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**ASSESSMENT OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES AND THE IMPACTS OF LAND USE
AND LAND COVER CHANGE IN A MASTERPLANNED CITY: THE CASE OF
FILINVEST CITY IN ALABANG, MUNTINLUPA**

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This Special Problem titled: “**ASSESSMENT OF ECOSYSTEM SERVICES AND THE IMPACTS OF LAND USE AND LAND COVER CHANGE IN A MASTERPLANNED CITY: THE CASE OF FILINVEST CITY IN ALABANG, MUNTINLUPA**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

Mark Daryll Overos 03/23/2025

Name

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ABSTRACT

Land in the Philippines has been subject to scarcity and overexploitation for the past years due to two of the many societal trends – population growth and continuous land degradation. In order to contribute to livable, safe, and sustainable communities, green spaces are recognized as a key element to navigate a variety of physical activities for the general public. Filinvest City in Muntinlupa was assessed to study its spatio-temporal changes, its impacts on ecosystem services, and the strategies in support for nature-based solutions. Data analysis was conducted through (1) QGIS and remote sensing to examine LULC change and landscape metrics, (2) reports synthesis on eco-profiling for biodiversity conservation assessment, and (3) ecosystem services assessment through survey. The results generated from remote sensing show integral data on the decrease of open land and rise of built-up areas between 2009 to 2015. On the other hand, Filinvest City showed high value on biodiversity preservation through maintenance and protection of its fauna (59% are resident breeder non-endemic bird species) and flora (47% are trees species). There is also significant correlation on the importance of ecosystem services functions with urban parks, recreational spaces, and biodiversity conservation. To further evaluate Filinvest City apart from study on ecosystem services and its impacts, it is recommended to conduct a (1) more up-to-date rapid biodiversity assessment and (2) analysis on urban heat island effect caused by green infrastructures replacing the natural land cover.

Keywords: Filinvest City, spatio-temporal changes, QGIS, remote sensing, ecosystem services, rapid biodiversity assessment

I. INTRODUCTION

Land in the Philippines has been subject to scarcity and overexploitation for the past years due to two of the many societal trends – population growth and continuous land degradation (Climate Diplomacy, n.d.). Land becomes scarce, especially in the rural areas due to increase also on the demand for basic human needs such as food sources and shelter. Although agricultural policies were introduced to improve land productivity, the farming systems posed unwanted consequences that damaged the agricultural land such as loss of natural habitats, groundwater depletion, and loss of biological diversity (Briones, 2005). Other forms of land exploitation are deforestation and agricultural land conversion, which all affect the natural flow of ecosystem processes.

Over time, land utilization and valuation has become one of the core fields in the business development sector. In order to contribute to livable, safe, and sustainable communities, green spaces are recognized as a key element to navigate a variety of physical activities for the general public. Public spaces have become an essential component of community life in supporting people-nature interaction and sustaining critical environmental functions. Some notable developments in the Philippines are the Arroceros Park in Ermita, Manila and Iloilo River Esplanade in Iloilo City which both recognize the significance of green open spaces, enhancing the quality of life and overall well-being of visitors, as well as preserving the biodiversity on these target areas. These public spaces also become an integral part of any masterplanned city, driven mainly by ecosystem services that enhance the community lifestyle.

II. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

To be able to examine the impact of land use and land cover change on ecosystem services of Filinvest City in Alabang, it is important to ponder on related studies that have been conducted. A number of journal articles and case studies will be considered to gather essential information needed to synthesize new and creative ideas for this research.

a. Ecosystem Services

With its aspiration to connect the human well-being to natural systems, ecosystem services (ES) are defined as all kinds of benefits that people obtain and acquire from its working environment. ES support and sustain human life through various contributions of nature such as food, water, nutrient cycle, and recreation. In principle, ES are classified into four categories – provisioning, regulating, cultural, and supporting ecosystem services. According to Deeksha & Shukla (2022), ES play a vital role in every individual by meeting the daily basic needs, maintaining healthy social relationships, and sustaining security provisions. They also highlighted the presence of urban ecosystems wherein 60% of ES around the world has been used inappropriately, resulting to a need for more comprehensive land use planning and environmental management. Haque & Sharifi (2024) also specified that ES are “crucial for urban resilience, climate change adaptation and mitigation, and sustainable development”. Equity and accessibility concerns are commonly addressed with reference to the presence of ecosystem services in urban areas. In addition to the research study of Haque and Sharifi, results showed that the natural ecosystems and green infrastructures are notably prioritized over

blue infrastructures. Moreover, emphasis on cultural and regulating services were of high significance in offering recreational activities and improving placemaking capabilities. With the interaction of various ecosystems, may it be natural or manmade, the study of ecosystem services becomes complex as relationships could bring out trade-offs or synergies (Braat & de Groot, 2012).

b. Biodiversity Conservation

With the critical threats and challenges to biodiversity faced by each region in the Philippines including deforestation, mining, and agricultural expansion, call for action to biodiversity conservation remains intact. According to Guerrero et al. (2021), effective conservation is evaluated through science-based evidence from gathered field data among various biodiversity hotspots. Consequently, comprehensive assessment on local situations is crucial to better implement effective interventions to areas, especially on identified pristine ecosystems. Agduma et al. (2023) emphasized on their journal article the relevance of understanding the biodiversity data on areas both with high levels of biodiversity and with lacking information. This simply highlights the need for a strengthened collaboration among various stakeholders, as well as pushing for centralized biodiversity information repository. Coupled with anthropogenic activities that severely harm ecosystems, critical impacts must be mitigated through biodiversity conservation efforts that will also be spearheaded by humans aiming for environmental changes.

c. Public Parks and Open Spaces

Public open spaces perceive to be an essential component of community life as these public assets contribute to livable, safe, and sustainable communities. These green spaces are key elements to navigate a variety of physical activities to the general public, may it be recreational or educational (Koohsari et al., 2015). The Presidential Decree No. 1216, or the Open Space Act of the Philippines, targets to create and maintain a healthy environment “by providing open spaces, roads, alleys, and sidewalks in residential subdivisions as may be deemed suitable to enhance the quality of life of the residents therein”. Amidst the existing law, the Philippines still is severely deficient in supply of public parks and open spaces with minimal to zero support from the government, according to an article of The Alliance for Safe, Sustainable, and Resilient Environments (n.d.). The urban landscape rapidly changes with the movement of population densities, climate change, and natural resources depletion, further demonstrating a requisite for provision of public open spaces.

d. Eco-Cities as Urban Solutions

Part of the vision by most developers, an eco-city is a form of human settlement which consists of structures and the natural environment that is self-sustaining. According to Bibri (2020), environmental policies promote eco-cities as the most environmentally sound model of sustainable urbanism. It challenges how project developers understand the need to elevate urbanization that will work hand in hand with economic progress. In addition, eco-cities are established to reinforce in minimizing social consequences and environmental stresses, providing an avenue to develop harmony between ecological system and urban social system (Hoai

Nguyen & Huong Thi Vu, 2023). Urbanization has exponentially evolved through the years especially in Asian countries like Singapore, Vietnam, Indonesia, and the Philippines. These land pockets converted into sustainable eco-cities are being acknowledged as the hidden gems for urban solution. Local and international microcosms continuously sprawl all over the world to further advocate for sustainable developments.

i. Local Microcosms

In the Philippine context, the evolution of various factors affecting the development of townships and parks has become evident, considering one of its major influences in the real estate realm – connectivity. According to an article by Leechiu (2023), most real estate developers started to adopt an active master-planning approach on land areas with greenfield locations in mid-1990s. To characterize, greenfield locations or sites belong under the umbrella term of undeveloped land commonly found in urban areas that are primarily used for agriculture (Hy-Tek Intralogistics, 2022). These sites pursue for commercial or residential use that will benefit both the developer in accordance with zoning regulations, and locals for additional job opportunities. Continuing the success of Makati and Ortigas central business districts (CBD) inside the Metro Manila commercial activity hub, a rebirth of integrated townships was conceptualized to create a live-work-play community that contains carefully planned pedestrians and vehicular infrastructure strategically located near transport hubs. With the likes of developments in the Greater Manila area (GMA) such as Cavite, Laguna, Bulacan, and Pampanga, there is a clear motive that all developments aim

to be accessible, holistic, and within reach. Consequently, effective planning of successful townships in the province intends to localize job opportunities, revitalize the economy, and reshape everyday lifestyle (Chua, 2023). Kept in mind are the presence of pedestrian-friendly open spaces, cycling lanes, and areas for future growth as the basic foundation for the development of sustainable townships.

1. Arroceros Forest Park

Positioned in the central district of Ermita, Manila is the 2.2-hectare Arroceros Forest Park, a riverside urban forest park recreated last 1992 by then Mayor Alfredo Lim, with Winner Foundation as the primary park custodian. Inhabited by 10 different kinds of birds and 60 types of Philippine tree species, the forest park served as a hub for environmental education and a recreational place for visitors to breath a hint of fresh air (Roces, 2007). The Arroceros Forest Park is considered as an urban forest where the transformed forest vegetation provides green open spaces to communities, enhancing social values of a stressful urban life towards sustainability. However, the park now is penned as the “last lung” of Manila, facing a number of challenges through severe degradation and negligence. According to an article of Ancheta et al. (2016), the Arroceros Forest Park is maintained with limited funding and awareness on its ecological value. Nonetheless, there are various advocacy groups and civil societies who are willing to protect the forest park from deterioration. In addition, high importance of air quality, climate, and temperature regulation summing up

to overall ecological value of the park are viewed as demands for the urban forest ecosystem services (Lagbas, 2019).

2. Iloilo River Esplanade

Iloilo River Esplanade is a promenade and linear park along the Iloilo River, created as part of the Iloilo River Rehabilitation Project. This park of green and blue spaces serves as an example of how a city can revamp its waterfronts, promote eco-friendly spaces, and enhance the quality of life for residents and visitors. According to the Provincial Environment and Natural Resources Officer (PENRO), the esplanade was a product of Iloilo's response to the long-standing pollution and negligence to Iloilo River which had suffered from industrial waste and improper waste disposal for years. With the rehabilitation of Iloilo River, the project has provided significant touchpoints on three pillars, to name a few – an economic development tool for attracting investments through increased foot traffic, launch of “eco-trail” app to Iloilo river eyed as an educational ecotourism hub in partnership with the University of the Philippines Visayas (UPV), and an avenue to preserve not only the river's ecological value (i.e. presence of endemic mangroves), but also reimagine its rich history and culture (Albay, 2021).

The design of Iloilo River Esplanade emphasized on introduction of modern infrastructures in fusion with natural elements. Complemented by lush greeneries, well-paved walkways are lined in the serene environment for jogging, cycling, and other recreational activities. In addition, existence of viewing decks and public art installations help enhance the overall visitor's experience. According to the journal article of Cruz et al. (2021), the

emergence of urban park served as a mitigation strategy to combat urban heat island phenomenon, providing a controlled cooling effect along the river edge, as well as targeting heat reduction and energy saving potential contributed by the tree-lined esplanade stretch.

The notable features captured both in Arroceros Park and Iloilo River Esplanade also are the key elements found in Filinvest City inside Alabang, Muntinlupa City – green open spaces, cycling trails and dedicated biking lanes, landscaped pathways, and family-friendly parks. For a land pocket to be considered as a master-planned city, it must carry the flagship feature of embracing the environmental solutions such as urban green space cooling effect, social benefits through recreational activities, and the economic advantages posed by these eco-cities.

e. Nature-Based Solutions

Designed to address major social issues such as food security, climate change, biodiversity loss, disaster risk reduction, and socio-economic development, nature-based solution is an ecosystem-related approach that measures to protect the ecosystems and ensure the well-being of people in their communities. It serves as a challenge to transition cities to become more climate resilient and livable in cohesion with the delivery of socio-economic and environmental aspects (Collier et al., 2023). Compared to technology-based solutions, nature-based solutions provide multiple synergistic benefits to various sectors and political goals such as green infrastructures and urban ecosystem-based adaptation. As highlighted in the Second Regional and Global Consultations on Nature-based Solutions in

Nairobi (2023), the Philippines presented insights on best practices to sustainably manage natural and altered ecosystems, as part of intergovernmental efforts. The Department of Environment and Natural Resources (DENR) introduced the country's National Greening Program and the Community-based Forest Management Strategy which both stresses the importance of involving local communities through forest landscape restoration and agroforestry in the height of sustainable management. In the context of introducing nature-based solutions in eco-cities, the estate management team commands an extensive analysis on biodiversity conservation of its township development.

As one of the pioneers in introducing garden central business districts in the country, Filinvest City provides an avenue to advocate the advantages of nature-based solutions. It encapsulates the main purpose and synergy among three pillars for sustainable development. Hampering one of its key elements may disturb the balance of developing a well-maintained and improving ecosystem. Thus, this kind of solution in addressing environmental issues paves way for a more sustainable environmental management.

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

As one of the master-planned cities promoting nature-based solutions, Filinvest City requires extensive analysis on the impact of land use and land cover change on ecosystem services.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To identify the ecosystem services provided by Filinvest City, a master planned township development in Metro South
- To determine and analyze land use and land cover change (LULC) patterns, landscape metrics, and their impacts on ecosystem services in Filinvest City
- To assess the greening programs and strategies that support nature-based solutions for ecosystem services and sustainable development in Filinvest City

V. RATIONALE

Filinvest City is a product of major land use and land cover change in an urban setting. Since 1995, the underutilized Alabang Stock Farm was transformed into a model of urban development across all economic facets – business, residential, leisure, medical, and educational. This eco-city also highlights the interconnection of three pillars of sustainability – a gateway for modern economic valuation, a hub for social interaction, and an open opportunity for environmental innovation.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

The research study on landscape analysis covers the 16-year period milestones of Filinvest City from 2005 to 2021, which includes the establishment of first residential projects and welcoming of business locators. Moreover, the biodiversity assessment report conducted by AECOM last 2018 was utilized in analyzing the existing biodiversity profile. Lastly, data gathering through survey consists of respondents who are mostly employees and residents of Filinvest City.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

Filinvest City (FC) is a visionary township development that provides modern convenience in harmony with nature. Sprawling over a vast 244-hectare fully integrated and self-contained township development project under the developer Filinvest Alabang, Inc., this former underutilized Alabang Stock Farm was transformed into a future-ready urban development that now provides a balanced mix of residential, institutional, leisure, medical, and business hubs. The township is also a preferred central business district in Metro Manila given that Filinvest City is highly accessible and is a gateway from North and South growth corridors. It fulfills a promise of providing a safe and convenient live-work-play community living with its privately-operated estate management team.

Included on the masterplan for FC is the provision of public open spaces – the Central Park, Linear Spectrum Park, and Creekside Park – as an essential component of community life through supporting people-nature interaction and sustaining critical environmental functions. One key element of FC is to embody a green community with open spaces as functional areas with lush landscape and tree-lined, shaded pathways like bike lanes and trails.

Figure 1. Filinvest City Map.

On top of these promises, FC was also awarded by U.S. Green Building Council the Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design v4 Gold for Neighborhood Development (LEEDv4 ND) certification, recognizing its design that are environmentally responsible from construction to maintenance. Apart from these greening efforts and recognitions, Filinvest City has also thrived in its socio-economic assets through the presence of its locators and ministry of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) who also support in achieving the sustainable development goals.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

Data analysis on the progress of Filinvest City through the years using QGIS and remote sensing will be done to examine LULC change and landscape metrics. An ecosystem services assessment will also be considered to gather both qualitative and quantitative data through survey forms. Moreover, reports on eco-profiling for biodiversity conservation assessment will be evaluated together with the results of land use and land cover change analysis.

a. LULC Landscape Analysis

This research study focuses on the use of Earth Explorer data aided by the path and row designation from the World Reference System (WRS) – a global notation system that offers satellite image portion designated by path and row numbers (Neigh et al., n.d.). The target zone of this study is path 116 row 50, covering Cavite, Laguna, and a part of Metro Manila. The satellite data are extracted from Earth Explorer, a service interface that provides reliable source of land remote-sensing data from U.S. Geological Survey or USGS (Educational Resources, n.d.). Aside from path/row and cloud cover, one important criterion is the timeline or range of data collection. In this study, a total of six datasets were acquired from 2005, 2009, 2015, 2018, 2020, and 2021. After generating all necessary satellite data records, land cover classification is created using Unsupervised Classification in Semi-Automatic Classification Plugin (SCP) from QGIS ver. 3 Hannover. SCP allows the user to classify, preprocess, and postprocess remote sensing images with supervision, as well as provide tools that are essential in the interpretation of data (Congedo, 2021).

Part of land cover classification is the categorization of four major sectors – water (sea, lake), vegetation (trees, forests), soil (bare/open land), and built up (buildings, infrastructures, roads). Landscape metrics are also extracted from the QGIS using landscape ecology statistics (LecoS) plugin. To fully analyze and measure the temporal changes in landscape structure, results were generated according to (1) land cover, (2) number of patches, (3) largest patch index, and (4) overall core area.

Figure 2. Flow chart of landscape analysis.

As indicated in the article of Li & Wu (2007), spatial patterns are described by the complexity (qualitative) and variability (quantitative) of a system property, which can be addressed through remote sensing. In the Philippine context, GIS mapping is vital in the study of various land change concerns such as industrialization and evolution of ecosystem services. These environmental and social implications will also be evaluated as major factors in the development of Filinvest City in Alabang.

b. Biodiversity Conservation Assessment

To assess the overall biodiversity within Filinvest City, a rapid biodiversity assessment tool will be employed to explore the different fauna and flora and conduct a species listing from various areas of the eco city. With the use of secondary data from the reports of Filinvest City, eco-profiling will also be facilitated as a biodiversity technique and will be evaluated in conjunction with the results of land use and land cover change analysis, providing a more comprehensive assessment on the effective master-planning efforts of Filinvest City.

c. Ecosystem Services Assessment

Primary data for ecosystem services assessment will be collected from wide range of people who have first-hand knowledge about Filinvest City including working professionals, residents, and visitors within the area through survey form. Quantitative data gathering through Likert scale and by asking dichotomous questions is essential in identifying present ecosystem services, their benefits to individuals, and its impact.

IX. RESULTS

A. LULC Landscape Analysis

The following data are extracted from QGIS to better understand the trend and landscape changes within Barangay Alabang, Muntinlupa City map section. The quantitative data focused on comparison of three land cover types – vegetation, open land, and built-up areas. The differences are presented in graphical form to highlight the significant trend for each classification.

1. Land Cover Classification

From 2005 to 2021, vegetation (green) and open lands (yellow) were dominated by built up areas (red) as observed from the landscape satellite images. The first two photos from Figure 3 show unclear visuals caused by parallel, slanted lines as these were captured using Landsat 7 ETM. The other images were extracted using Landsat 8 which has more precise spectral bands and geometry (Irons et al., 2012). Visible clouds are accounted as water bodies due to probable water evaporation from the Laguna Lake at the right. Rapid emergence of built-up structures and depletion of open land are evident from 2015 onwards, significantly due to the rise of commercial and industrial areas in the south.

2. Landscape Pattern Analysis

a. Land Cover Area

Land cover area is measured to see how much of the landscape is comprised of a specific land cover type, as well as to analyze the change of extent of the land classifications (Borana & Yadav, 2017). The result from Figure 4 shows that in more than a decade, good control over vegetated land is visible from 2005 to 2020, there was a decrease in open land at 59

million sqm minimum, and growth of built up areas at 327 million sqm maximum.

Figure 4. Temporal land cover area changes covering Muntinlupa City portion.

b. Number of Patches

The number of patches, as shown in Figure 5, utilize and quantify the land cover classifications. Vegetation patches stopped to surge after the year 2015. Open lands have proliferated from 2009 to 2020, with similar trend as to built up areas. These records signify a shift from vegetation to open lands, in preparation for construction of establishments and infrastructures.

c. Largest Patch Index

According to Borana & Yadav (2017), this landscape metric assesses the landscape occupied by largest patch type. The largest patch of vegetation land is from year 2018, with evident open land degradation and increase in built up zones from 2015 (see Figure 6).

Figure 3. Landsat images of landscape structure of Manila-Cavite-Laguna map from (a) 2005, (b) 2009, (c) 2015, (d) 2018, (e) 2020, and (f) 2021.

Figure 5. Number of patches land cover type in Muntinlupa City portion.

Figure 6. Changes in patch index proportion covered by largest patch type.

d. Overall Core Area

This landscape metric indicates the total area within patches present in the ecosystem and is an important factor in ecological processes that affects all types of organisms such as predation, competition, and even anthropogenic intervention (McGarigal & Marks, 1995). As observed in Figure 7, vegetation land area has decreased since 2018, and open land

depletion is evidently a factor in the rise of built-up zones from 70 sqm in 2015 to 100 sqm in 2018. These patches show results of land fragmentation that both provide benefits and disadvantages to different human sectors.

Figure 7. Changes in total core area of land cover types in Muntinlupa City portion.

B. Biodiversity Conservation Assessment

The rapid biodiversity assessment report conducted within Filinvest City was shared by the Filinvest Estate Team as part of research area eco-profiling. A list of recorded plants and wildlife species were captured during the transect walk and walkthrough surveys gathered by AECOM last 2018 and provided a summary of species listing as shown in Appendix B. A graphical representation was provided in Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 to show the comparison of plant species in terms of growth forms and endemism. Out of 121 plant species collected, 47% are classified as trees. Among the 24 tree family species, 21% are under the Fabaceae family (pea such as narra, balitbitan, and sampalok tree) and 18% are under the Moraceae family (mulberry such as is-is and antipolo tree). These tree types are commonly located along the urban parks of Filinvest City such as Central Park and Linear Spectrum Park. In terms of endemism, 55% are considered exotic or not native to the area that displaces the

native species and alters the natural systems. Date palm trees, which are over 3,000 in actual count, are incorporated into the landscape and are considered as a trademark of Filinvest City lined up in its main streets such as Corporate Avenue and Commerce Avenue. Around 42% are considered native or indigenous but non-endemic which existed for many years in the area such as the banaba, bangkal, and narra trees.

Figure 8. Plant species in terms of growth forms in Filinvest City.

Figure 9. Plant species in terms of endemism (NNE - native but non-endemic; PE - Philippine endemic; CBD - cannot be determined).

With its aspiration to preserve the biodiversity for both flora and faunas, Filinvest City includes the establishment of bird sanctuary in their long-term pipeline of strategies. Part of the biodiversity assessment report is the recording of wildlife species during transect walks, especially the determination of a variety of birds. In terms of range distribution, Figure 10 shows that almost 59% of bird species present in the surroundings of Filinvest City are resident breeder non-endemic. These kinds of birds do not have a defined geographic area but tend to remain on breeding grounds and considered Filinvest City as their nesting location. Examples of these are the long-tailed shrike, large-billed crow, and white-collared kingfisher which are commonly seen along Palms District.

Figure 10. Bird species in terms of range distribution (RBNE – resident breeder non-endemic; RBP – resident breeding populations; LE – Luzon endemic).

Moreover, part of the report is the determination if these bird species are listed under IUCN red list of threatened species 2017, where all resulted to be categorized under the least concern version. Out of 41 recorded species, only one was identified

to be endangered under DENR AO 2004-15 - Establishing the list of terrestrial Threatened Species and their Categories, and the list of other Wildlife Species Pursuant to RA 9147 of 2001. The osprey migratory bird, or *Pandion haliaetus*, was also included under Appendix II of Convention on International Trade of Endangered Species (CITES) of Wild Flora and Fauna 2017 which certifies the banning of international trade in species under threat. This set of data provides an insight into the urgent need for biodiversity protection within Filinvest City, as well as firming up probable solutions in rallying for enhanced ecosystem services.

C. Ecosystem Services Assessment

The survey sample consist of 29 female and 21 male respondents, mostly ranging from 22 to 29 years of age. 84% are single individuals who are either residents or employees from business locators inside Filinvest City. Around 48% have a household size above five, with monthly income ranging from Php 26,000 to Php 50,000. For most respondents, both their area of residence (36%) and hometown (50%) are situated in Laguna province next to Muntinlupa City. When asked about the respondent's liking on future developments within Alabang, the level of understanding on ecosystem services functions, and their willingness to pay (see Table 1), data using Jamovi statistics software shows that the mean ranges from 3.31 to 4.74 or above average rating with a standard deviation of 0.50 to 0.92 (see Fig. 11). The respondents are perceived to have high confidence in the potential of Filinvest City to prosper and benefit from ecosystem services through more urban parks, recreational spaces, and efforts for biodiversity preservation.

Figure 11. Descriptive analysis on level of interest, level of understanding on ecosystem services functions and their willingness to pay using Jamovi.

Descriptives

	Interest in Alabang development in 10-15 years	Level of understanding on ecosystem services	Level of importance of ecosystem services functions	Level of importance of urban parks	Level of importance of recreational spaces	Level of importance of biodiversity preservation	Willingness to pay for maintenance of ES functions
N	39	39	39	39	39	39	39
Mean	4.46	3.74	4.62	4.74	4.69	4.72	3.31
Standard deviation	0.790	0.818	0.590	0.498	0.521	0.510	0.922

In terms of willingness to pay for the maintenance of these ecosystem services functions, around 57% of the respondents are willing to donate an annual fee of less than Php 25,000, while an average of 39% are not willing to pay for the said purpose. One of the main reasons why they declined to pay or donate is that they believe the Filinvest estate team (67%), and the local government (75%) should bear the cost of maintaining the ecosystem services functions in Filinvest City. Additional comments include the potential for these public spaces to be improperly monetized, could be a hindrance for visitors who cannot afford the charging fees, and the unfair allocation of fees for Filinvest City residents and visitors.

Table 1

Likert scale questionnaire to quantify the level of understanding and importance of ecosystem services in Filinvest City, Alabang

Survey Questions	Very interested/ strongly agree/ very willing	Agree/ Willing	Neutral	Disagree/ Unwilling	Very not interested/ strongly disagree/ very unwilling
Interest in Alabang development over in 10 to 15 years	5	4	3	2	1
Level of understanding on ecosystem services	5	4	3	2	1

Level of importance of ecosystem services functions	5	4	3	2	1
Level of importance of urban parks	5	4	3	2	1
Level of importance of recreational spaces	5	4	3	2	1
Level of importance of biodiversity preservation	5	4	3	2	1
Willingness to pay for maintenance of ES functions	5	4	3	2	1

These remarks show that a high percentage of willingness to pay has no significant association with the respondent's high level of interest in further development of ecosystem services in Filinvest City. Nonetheless, there is a need for cost-benefit analysis from Filinvest estate team and local government to implement desired efforts in enriching the capacity of Filinvest City as a sustainable eco-city.

Moreover, respondents were also asked about the key factors to be considered in eyeing nature-based solutions in Filinvest City. Figure 12 provides an insight into prioritizing the most the impact of further developments to the ecological environment, followed by the benefits it will bring for human satisfaction. In compliance with maintaining 30% of open public spaces for township development, it is expected for the developer to introduce more strategic efforts that will highlight incorporation of green projects amidst continuing land cover changes in Filinvest City.

Figure 12. Factors affecting ecosystem services in Filinvest City for policy consideration.

X. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

Land use and land cover change are evident in Filinvest City, Alabang from its conception in 1995 due to land valuation, population growth, and increase in land demand for industrialization. Land fragmentation was highlighted in this study to check probable causes and effects of this project. Landsat images and datasets through QGIS software were taken in six time periods from 2005 to 2021, and land cover types were classified as vital in this research analysis. The results generated from landscape metrics such as land cover, number of patches, largest patch index, and overall core area, show integral data on the decrease of open lands and rise of built-up areas between 2009 to 2015. These changes provided environmental and social impacts that primarily affected the locals and businesses within Muntinlupa City. Nonetheless, one major benefit of this project was the provision of jobs and more opportunities for livelihood to residents and visitors in the area. This information and environmental factors are deemed essential in the post processing evaluation of the project and to succeeding plans for the country.

Aside from the provision of job opportunities to individuals, Filinvest City also values biodiversity preservation through maintenance and protection of its fauna (59% are resident breeder non-endemic bird species) and flora (47% are trees species). Results from biodiversity eco-profiling assessment report conducted last 2018 show species diversity amidst changes in land use and land cover. Consequently, there is significant correlation on the importance of ecosystem services functions with urban parks, recreational spaces, and biodiversity conservation. There is high acceptability of respondents on the introduction of more nature-based solutions in the research

area, prioritizing the impact on the ecological environment that suits the aspirations of Filinvest City as a master-planned township development in the Metro South.

XI. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

This paper aimed to analyze the spatio-temporal changes in Filinvest City, its impacts to ecosystem services, and the strategies in support for nature-based solutions as a tool for sustainable development. The ecosystem services are considered as a bloodstream for sustained biodiversity preservation within an eco-city, which contributes to promoting urban solutions. Amidst changes in land use and land cover, a rich species diversity remains evident with the presence of exotic (55%) and native but non-endemic (42%) plant species which existed for many years within Filinvest City, as well as the existence of resident breeder non-endemic (59%) bird species which considered Filinvest City as their nesting location. All these firms up the need for more solutions in enhancing additional offerings in a master-planned city. Therefore, the impact on humans and ecological environment is a primary priority in crafting policy considerations.

To further evaluate Filinvest City apart from study on ecosystem services and its impacts, it is recommended to conduct a new rapid biodiversity assessment through transect walk survey within Filinvest City to better assess an up-to-date monitoring of species, post-pandemic. Moreover, an analysis on urban heat island effect caused by green infrastructures replacing the natural land cover can be considered. This does not only provide a holistic insight into other aspects of the city's environmental impacts such as heat and air quality, but also highlights the importance of nature-based solutions integration inside a central business district.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A: SURVEY FORM QUESTIONS

Socio-demographic Profile and Basic Information

What is your gender?

Male Female

What is your age?

<29 years 30-39 years 40-49 years 50-59 years 60-69 years over 70 years

What is your marital status?

Single Married

What is your educational attainment?

Highschool College

How many people are in your household?

1 2 3 4 5 and above

What is your monthly income?

prefer not to disclose < Php 25,000 Php 26,000-50,000 Php 51,000-75,000

Php 76,000-100,000 above Php 100,000

What is your area of residence?

within Muntinlupa City within Metro Manila Cavite Laguna Batangas Rizal

What area is your hometown?

within Muntinlupa City within Metro Manila Cavite Laguna Batangas Rizal

Relevance to Study Area

Overall, how interested are you in the development of Filinvest City, Alabang over the next 10 to 15 years? (*Rating: 5 as very interested to 1 as not at all*)

How well do you understand what ecosystem services are? (*Rating: 5 as very well to 1 as not at all*)

To what extent do you agree that the function of ecosystem services is important?

(Rating: 5 as very well to 1 as not at all)

Have you participated in research related to ecosystem services?

- Yes, with experience as an investigator/assistant
- No, but I have heard of this research
- No, I have never heard of this research

How important is the provision of urban parks as an ecosystem service based on your perception and experience? *(Rating: 5 as very important to 1 as not important)*

How important is the emergence of recreational spaces as an ecosystem service based on your perception and experience? *(Rating: 5 as very important to 1 as not important)*

How important is the biodiversity preservation as an ecosystem service based on your perception and experience? *(Rating: 5 as very important to 1 as not important)*

Willingness to Pay

Are you willing to donate a reasonable fee to maintain the ecosystem service functions within Filinvest City? (This is a hypothetical question, and you will not incur any actual expenses. We ask this question only to understand the value of these ecosystem services in the research area) *(Rating: 5 as very willing to 1 as very unwilling)*

The maintenance of urban parks (Central Park, Spectrum Linear Park, and Creekside Park) in Filinvest City can contribute to area development and cultural advancement.

If a monetary donation is necessary to maintain cleanliness and order within these open public spaces, what is the maximum amount you are willing to pay per year?

- 0
- < Php 25,000
- Php 26,000-50,000
- Php 51,000-75,000
- Php 76,000-100,000
- above Php 100,000

The maintenance of recreational services (Central Park Stage, Filinvest City Art) in Filinvest City can contribute to boost tourism and foot traffic. If a monetary donation is necessary to maintain the areas for recreation, what is the maximum amount you are willing to pay per year?

- 0
- < Php 25,000
- Php 26,000-50,000
- Php 51,000-75,000
- Php 76,000-100,000
- above Php 100,000

The maintenance of biodiversity preservation (Botanical Garden, Bird Sanctuary) in Filinvest City can contribute to fauna and flora conservation. If a monetary donation is necessary to maintain the areas for ecotourism and education, what is the maximum amount you are willing to pay per year?

- 0
- < Php 25,000
- Php 26,000-50,000
- Php 51,000-75,000
- Php 76,000-100,000
- above Php 100,000

Why did you answer “very unwilling” or indicate a payment amount of “Php 0”? Please select all that apply.

- Maintaining the ecosystem services functions in Filinvest City has no value to me
- The Filinvest City Estate team should bear the cost of maintaining the ecosystem services functions in Filinvest City
- The local government should bear the cost of maintaining the ecosystem services functions in Filinvest City
- I disagree with using money for this purpose
- Others

Factors to consider when selecting a suitable nature-based solution for Filinvest City

If you were to introduce a program to improve the capacity of Filinvest City to serve its community, which of the following policy considerations would you recommend the most?

- Overall ecosystem services for human satisfaction
- Economic cost of investment
- Impact on the ecological environment
- Social acceptance

If you were to implement a program/solution to improve the capacity of Filinvest City to serve its community, how would you rank the following considerations from most (1) to least (4) important?

- Overall ecosystem services for human satisfaction
- Economic cost of investment
- Impact on the ecological environment
- Social acceptance

APPENDIX B: FILINVEST CITY RAPID BIODIVERSITY ASSESSMENT REPORT

2018

A. List of Recorded Plant Species in Filinvest City during the Transect Walk/

Walkthrough Surveys Conducted last April 11, 2018

Families	Scientific Names	Common Names	Growth Forms	Endemicity
ACANTHACEAE	<i>Lepidagathis secunda</i> (Blanco) Nees	sipsipan (Tag.)	herb	NNE
ACANTHACEAE	<i>Thunbergia grandiflora</i> Roxb.	sky flower (Engl.)	climber	Exotic
ACANTHACEAE	<i>Barleria cristata</i> L.	Philippine violet (Engl.)	shrub	Exotic
AMARANTHACEAE	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) DC	lupug-lupug (Bis.)	herb	NNE
AMARANTHACEAE	<i>Cyathula prostrata</i> (L.) Blume	hookweed (Engl.)	herb	NNE
AMARANTHACEAE	<i>Amaranthus gracilis</i> Desf.	kulitis (Tag.)	herb	Exotic
AMARANTHACEAE	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	bayambang (Tag.)	herb	Exotic
ANACARDIACEAE	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	mangga (Tag.), mango (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
ANACARDIACEAE	<i>Buchanania arborescens</i> Blume	balinghasai (Tag.)	tree	NNE
ANACARDIACEAE	<i>Semecarpus cuneiformis</i> Blanco	ligas (Tag.)	tree	NNE
ANNONACEAE	<i>Polyalthia longifolia</i> Benth. & Hook f.	India lanutan (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
APOCYNACEAE	<i>Wrightia pubescens</i> R. Br.	lanete (Tag.)	tree	NNE
APOCYNACEAE	<i>Tabernaemontana pandacaqui</i> Poir ssp. Laniti (Blanco)	pandakaki (Tag.)	tree	NNE
APOCYNACEAE	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R. Br.	dita (Tag.)	tree	NNE
APOCYNACEAE	<i>Plumeria acuminata</i> Ait.	kalachuchi (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
ARACEAE	<i>Xanthosoma sagittifolium</i> (L.) Schott.	gabi-gabihan (Tag.)	herb	NNE
ARACEAE	<i>Dieffenbachia amoena</i> Bull.	bakya (Tag.)	herb	Exotic
ARACEAE	<i>Colocasia esculenta</i> (L.) Shott.	gabi (Tag.)	herb	Exotic
ARACEAE	<i>Epipremnum pinnatum</i> (L.) Engl.	tibatib (Tag.)	climber	NNE
ARACEAE	<i>Philodendron bipinnatifidum</i> Schott. ex Endl.	selloum (Engl.)	climber	Exotic
ARALIACEAE	<i>Schefflera arboricola</i> (Hayata) Kanehira	variegated schefflera (Engl.)	shrub	Exotic
ARECACEAE	<i>Ptychosperma macarthurii</i> (H. Wendl.) Nichols	McArthur palm (Engl.)	palm	Exotic
ARECACEAE	<i>Adonidia merrillii</i> (Becc.) Becc.	Manila palm (Engl.)	palm	NNE
ARECACEAE	<i>Phoenix dactylifera</i> L.	date palm (Engl.)	palm	Exotic
ARECACEAE	<i>Licuala grandis</i> H. Wendl.	balatbat-bilog (Tag.)	palm	Exotic
ASTERACEAE	<i>Mikania cordata</i> (Burm.) B. L. Robinson	ooko (Tag.)	climber	Exotic
ASTERACEAE	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	tridax daisy (Engl.)	herb	Exotic

ASTERACEAE	Cyanthium cinereum (L.) H. Robinson	tagulinau (Tag.)	herb	Exotic
BIGNONIACEAE	Mansoa hymenaea DC. A Gentry	garlic vine (Engl.)	climber	Exotic
BIGNONIACEAE	Spathodea campanulata Beauv.	African tulip tree (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
BIGNONIACEAE	Tabebuia pallida (Lindl.) Miers	Cuban pink trumpet tree (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
BORAGINACEAE	Ehretia resinosa Hance	talibunog (Tag.)	tree	NNE
BORAGINACEAE	Ehretia microphylla Lam.	tsaang gubat (Tag.)	shrub	NNE
CAPPARIDACEAE	Capparis micracantha DC	halubagat (Tag.)	shrub	NNE
CAPPARIDACEAE	Capparis floribunda Wight.	halubagat babae (Tag.)	shrub	NNE
COMBRETACEAE	Terminalia catappa L.	talisai (Tag.)	tree	NNE
COMMELINACEAE	Murdannia sp.		herb	NNE
CONNARACEAE	Connarus sp.		climber	NNE
CONVOLVULACEAE	Ipomoea aquatica Forssk.	kangkong (Tag.)	herb	Exotic
CONVOLVULACEAE	Merremia sp.		climber	NNE
COSTACEAE	Cheilocostus speciosus (J. Konig.) C. Specht.	spiral ginger (Engl.)	herb	Exotic
CYPERACEAE	Cyperus alternifolius L.	umbrella plant (Engl.)	sedge	Exotic
EUPHORBIACEAE	Macaranga tanarius (L.) Muell.-Arg.	binunga (Tag.)	tree	NNE
EUPHORBIACEAE	Melanolepis multiglandulosa (Reinw. ex Blume) Reichb. & Zoll.	alim (tag.)	tree	NNE
EUPHORBIACEAE	Acalypha indica L.	maratong (Ilk.)	herb	Exotic
EUPHORBIACEAE	Manihot esculenta Crantz.	cassava (Engl.)	shrub	Exotic
EUPHORBIACEAE	Excoecaria cochinchinensis Lour.	firestorm (Engl.)	shrub	Exotic
FABACEAE	Leucaena leucocephala (Lam.) de Wit.	ipil-ipil (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
FABACEAE	Centrosema pubescens Benth.	pukinggan (Tag.)	climber	Exotic
FABACEAE	Tamarindus indica L.	sampalok (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
FABACEAE	Albizia saman F. Muell.	akasya (Tag.), rain tree (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
FABACEAE	Gliricidia sepium (Jacq.) HBK	kakawate (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
FABACEAE	Cassia fistula L.	caña-fistula (Sp.)	tree	Exotic
FABACEAE	Pterocarpus indicus Willd.	narra (Tag.)	tree	NNE
FABACEAE	Senna siamea (Lam.) Irwin & Barneby	Thailand shower (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
FABACEAE	Peltoporum pterocarpum (DC) Back ex K. Heyne	siar (Tag.)	tree	NNE
FABACEAE	Delonix regia (Boj. ex Hook.) Raf.	fire tree (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
FABACEAE	Cynometra ramiflora L.	balitbitan (Tag.)	tree	NNE
FABACEAE	Dalbergia sp.		climber	NNE
FABACEAE	Acacia auriculiformis A. Cunn. ex Benth.	auri (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
FABACEAE	Erythrina fusca Lour.	purple coral tree (Engl.)	tree	Exotic

HELICONIACEAE	Heliconia psittacorum L. f.	parrots flower (Engl.)	herb	Exotic
LAMIACEAE	Callicarpa formosana Rolfe	beauty berry (Engl.)	shrub	NNE
LAURACEAE	Persea americana Mill.	avocado (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
LAURACEAE	Litsea glutinosa (Lour.) C. B. Rob.	sablot (Ilk.)	tree	NNE
LEMNACEAE	Lemna paucicostata Hegelm.	liya (Tag.)	herb	Exotic
LILIACEAE	Liriope muscari (Decne) L. H. Bailey	variegated liriope (Engl.)	herb	Exotic
LORANTHACEAE	Scurrula ferruginea (Jack) Danser		mistletoe	NNE
LYTHRACEAE	Cuphea hyssopifolia HBK	Singapore bush (Engl.)	herb	Exotic
LYTHRACEAE	Lagerstroemia speciosa (L.) Pers.	banaba (Tag.)	tree	NNE
MAGNOLIACEAE	Michelia champaca L.	champaka (Hindu)	tree	Exotic
MELIACEAE	Azadirachta indica A. Juss.	neem tree (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
MELIACEAE	Swietenia macrophylla King	large-leaved mahogany (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
MORACEAE	Ficus cumingii Miq.	is-is ibon (Tag.)	tree	NNE
MORACEAE	Ficus septica Burm. f.	hauili (Tag.)	tree	NNE
MORACEAE	Ficus ulmifolia Lam.	is-is (Tag.)	tree	PE
MORACEAE	Ficus nota (Blanco) Merr.	tibig (Tag.)	tree	NNE
MORACEAE	Ficus concinna Miq.	pasapla (Ilk.)	tree	NNE
MORACEAE	Artocarpus blancoi (Elmer) Merr.	antipolo (Tag.)	tree	PE
MORACEAE	Streblus asper Lour.	kalios (Tag.)	tree	NNE
MORACEAE	Ficus benjamina L.	salisi (Tag.)	tree	NNE
MORACEAE	Ficus religiosa L.	bo tree (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
MORACEAE	Ficus elastica Roxb.	India rubber (Engl.)	tree	Exotic
MORINGACEAE	Moringa oleifera Lam.	malunggay (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
MUNTINGIACEAE	Muntingia calabura L.	datiles (Tag.), aratilis (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
MUSACEAE	Musa x paradisiaca L.	saging (Tag.)	herb	Exotic
MYRTACEAE	Syzygium cumini (L.) Skeels	duhat (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
MYRTACEAE	Eugenia sp.		shrub	Exotic
NYCTAGINACEAE	Bougainvillea spectabilis Willd.	bougainvillea (Engl.)	shrub	Exotic
NYCTAGINACEAE	Pisonia alba Span.	maluko (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
NYMPHAEACEAE	Nymphaea sp.	lotus Engl.)	herb	Exotic
PHYLLANTHACEAE	Antidesma bunius (L.) Spreng	bignai (Tag.)	tree	NNE
PHYLLANTHACEAE	Securinega virosa (Roxb. ex Willd.) Baill.		shrub	NNE
PHYLLANTHACEAE	Phyllanthus amarus Schumach. & Thonn.	sampaluk-sampalukan (Tag.)	herb	NNE
PHYLLANTHACEAE	Phyllanthus urinaria L.	iba-iba-an (Tag.)	herb	NNE
PHYTOLACCACEAE	Rivinia humilis L.	rivinia (Engl.)	herb	Exotic
POACEAE	Chloris gayana Kunth.		grass	Exotic
POACEAE	Panicum maximum Jacq.	guinea grass (Engl.)	grass	Exotic
POACEAE	Bambusa vulgaris Schrad ex. Wendl.	kauayang kiling (Tag.)	bamboo	Exotic

POACEAE	Panicum sp.		grass	NNE
POACEAE	Axonopus compressus (Sw.) P Beauv		grass	NNE
POACEAE	Bambusa blumeana J.A. & J.H. Schultz	kauayang tinik (Tag.)	bamboo	NNE
POACEAE	Dichanthium aristatum (Poir.) C.E. Hubb.	alabang x (Engl.)	grass	Exotic
POACEAE	Digitaria ciliaris (Retz.) Koel		grass	Exotic
PODOCARPACEAE	Podocarpus sp.		tree	Exotic
POLYGONACEAE	Triplaris cumingiana Fisch & Mey	palo santo (Sp.)	tree	Exotic
PONTEDERIACEAE	Monochoria vaginalis (Burm. f.) C Presl	gabing-uak (Tag.)	herb	NNE
PORTULACACEAE	Portulaca oleracea L.	gulasiman (Tag.)	herb	Exotic
PTERIDACEAE	Pteris ensiformis Burm.f.		fern	NNE
RUBIACEAE	Nauclea orientalis L.	bangkal (Tag.)	tree	NNE
RUBIACEAE	Morinda citrifolia L.	bangkoro (Tag.), apatot (Tag.)	tree	NNE
RUTACEAE	Murraya paniculata (L.) Jack	kamuning (Tag.)	shrub	NNE
SAPINDACEAE	Lepisanthes sp.		tree	NNE
SAPINDACEAE	Guioa koelreuteria (Blanco) Merr.	alahan (Tag.)	tree	NNE
SAPINDACEAE	Filicium decipiens (Wight. & Arn.)Thwaites ex Hook. F.	fern tree (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
SAPOTACEAE	Chrysophyllum cainito L.	star apple (Engl.), caimito (Tag.)	tree	Exotic
SAPOTACEAE	Mimusops elengi L.	kabiki (Tag.)	tree	NNE
URTICACEAE	Pipturus asper Wedd.		tree	NNE
VERBENACEAE	Duranta erecta L.	pigeon berry (Engl.)	shrub	Exotic
VITACEAE	Tetrastigma sp.		climber	CBD
ZINGIBERACEAE	Curcuma domestica Valetton	luyang dilaw (Tag.)	herb	Exotic

B. List of Recorded Wildlife Species in Filinvest City during Transect Walks

Conducted from April 10 to 14, 2018

No	Type	Scientific Names	Common Names	Range Distribution	Conservation Status (IUCN 2017)	CITES 2017	RA 9147 (DENR AO 2004-15)
1	Birds	Alcedo atthis	common kingfisher	migrant	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
2	Birds	Amaurornis phoenicurus	white-breasted waterhen	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
3	Birds	Aplonis panayensis	Asian glossy starling	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included

4	Birds	Bubulcus ibis	cattle egret	migrant w/ rbp	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
5	Birds	Centropus bengalensis	lesser coucal	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
6	Birds	Centropus viridis	Philippine coucal	PE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
7	Birds	Collocalia esculenta	glossy swiftlet	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
8	Birds	Collocalia troglodytes	pygmy swiftlet	PE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
9	Birds	Copsychus saularis	Oriental magpie-robin	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
10	Birds	Corvus macrorhynchos	large-billed crow	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
11	Birds	(Dendrocopos) Picoides maculatus	Philippine pygmy woodpecker	PE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
12	Birds	Dicaeum australe	red-keeled flowerpecker	PE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
13	Birds	Egretta garzetta	little egret	migrant	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
14	Birds	(Gallirallus) Hypotaenidia torquata	barred rail	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
15	Birds	Gerygone sulphurea	golden-bellied flyeater	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
16	Birds	Geopelia striata	zebra dove	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
17	Birds	(Halcyon) Todiramphus chloris	white-collared kingfisher	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
18	Birds	Halcyon smyrnensis	white-throated kingfisher	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
19	Birds	Hirundo tahitica	Pacific swallow	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
20	Birds	Hirundo rustica	barn swallow	migrant	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
21	Birds	Ixobrychus cinnamomeus	cinnamon bittern	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
22	Birds	Ixobrychus sinensis	yellow bittern	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
23	Birds	Lalage nigra	pieb triller	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
24	Birds	Lanius cristatus	brown shrike	migrant w/ rbp	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
25	Birds	Lanius schach	long-tailed shrike	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included

26	Birds	Lonchura malacca	chestnut munia	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
27	Birds	Lonchura punctulata	scaly-breasted munia	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
28	Birds	(Megalaima) Psilopogon haemacephala	coppersmith barbet	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
29	Birds	Megalurus palustris	striated grassbird	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
30	Birds	Merops viridis	blue-throated bee-eater	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
31	Birds	Motacilla cinerea	grey wagtail	migrant	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
32	Birds	Muscicapa griseisticta	grey-streaked flycatcher	migrant	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
33	Birds	(Nectarinia) Cinnerys jugularis	olive-backed sunbird	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
34	Birds	Nycticorax nycticorax	black-crowned night-heron	migrant	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
35	Birds	Oriolus chinensis	black-naped oriole	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
36	Birds	Passer montanus	Eurasian tree sparrow	introduced	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
37	Birds	Pandion haliaetus	osprey	migrant	LC ver. 3.1	Appendix II	Endangered
38	Birds	Phapitreron leucotis	white-eared brown-dove	PE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
39	Birds	Pycnonotus goiavier	yellow-vented bulbul	RBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
40	Birds	Rhipidura nigritorquis	Philippine pied fantail	PE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
41	Birds	Zosterops meyeri	lowland white-eye	LE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
42	Amphibians and Reptiles	Rhinella marina	cane toad	introduced	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included
43	Amphibians and Reptiles	Pelodiscus sinensis	Chinese softshell turtle	introduced	Vulnerable ver 2.3	Not included	Not included
44	Amphibians and Reptiles	Eutropis multifasciata	many-lined sun skink	NBNE	NYBA	Not included	Not included
45	Amphibians and Reptiles	Gecko gekko	tokay gecko	NBNE	NYBA	Not included	Not included
46	Amphibians and Reptiles	Hemidactylus frenatus	common house gecko	NBNE	LC ver. 3.1	Not included	Not included

Legend:

RBNE - resident breeder non-endemic

migrant w/ rbp - migrant with resident breeding populations

PE - Philippine endemic

LE - Luzon endemic

NNE/ NBNE - native but non-endemic

LC ver. 3.1 - Least Concern version 3.1 (The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2017-3)

RA 9147 - Philippine Wildlife Act of 2001 (Conservation and Protection of Wildlife Resources and their Habitats)

DENR AO 2004-15 - Establishing the list of terrestrial Threatened Species and their Categories, and the list of other Wildlife Species Pursuant to RA 9147 of 2001 IUCN 2017 - The IUCN Red List of Threatened Species. Version 2017-3

CITES 2017 - Convention on International Trade of Endangered Species (CITES) of Wild Flora and Fauna 2017

APPENDIX C: SURVEY DATA RESULTS USING JAMOVI

Frequencies of Level of importance of recreational spaces

Level of importance of recreational spaces	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
3	1	2.6 %	2.6 %
4	10	25.6 %	28.2 %
5	28	71.8 %	100.0 %

Level of importance of biodiversity reservation	Willingness to pay for maintenance of ES functions
39	39
4.72	3.31
0.510	0.922

Frequencies of Level of importance of biodiversity preservation

Level of importance of biodiversity preservation	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
3	1	2.6 %	2.6 %
4	9	23.1 %	25.6 %
5	29	74.4 %	100.0 %

Frequencies of Willingness to pay for maintenance of ES functions

Willingness to pay for maintenance of ES functions	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
1	1	2.6 %	2.6 %
2	5	12.8 %	15.4 %
3	18	46.2 %	61.5 %
4	11	28.2 %	89.7 %
5	4	10.3 %	100.0 %

Level of understanding on ecosystem services	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
2	2	5.1 %	5.1 %
3	13	33.3 %	38.5 %
4	17	43.6 %	82.1 %
5	7	17.9 %	100.0 %

Frequencies of Level of importance of ecosystem services functions

Level of importance of ecosystem services functions	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
3	2	5.1 %	5.1 %
4	11	28.2 %	33.3 %
5	26	66.7 %	100.0 %

Frequencies of Level of importance of urban parks

Level of importance of urban parks	Counts	% of Total	Cumulative %
3	1	2.6 %	2.6 %
4	8	20.5 %	23.1 %
5	30	76.9 %	100.0 %